

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF PLASMA-ARC SPRAYING OF CURRENT-CONDUCTING WIRES MADE OF MATERIALS WITH INCREASED AFFINITY TO OXYGEN

*Korzhyk V.,
Sitko O.,
Strohonov D.,
Popov Ie.,
Khaskin V.,
Tischenko O.,
Yulyugin V.,
Vorobyiov V.,
Yarosh V.*

*E.O. Paton Electric Welding Institute of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Kyiv, Ukraine*

Abstract

The article is devoted to determining the propensity for oxygen saturation of materials with increased affinity for oxygen during their plasma-arc spraying in the case of using the process of spraying moving anode wires. It was established that the selected scheme of spraying with a moving wire-anode with plasma compression by a flow of accompanying shielding gas (air) ensures reduced oxidation of the sprayed electrode material. To detect such an effect during plasma-arc spraying of electrode wires from materials containing elements with increased affinity for oxygen, the oxygen content in the sprayed coatings was investigated. At the same time, it was established that this oxygen content is: 1.1-1.2 wt. % – for Cu99 copper, 3.4-4.4 wt. % – for aluminum-magnesium alloy 5083.

Keywords: plasma-arc spraying, moving anode wires, oxidation, elements with increased affinity for oxygen.

The creation of new powder materials requires, on the one hand, the complication of the technological process with an increase in the number of redistributions, on the other hand, the involvement of new physical methods [1]. The complexity of the technology and the increase in the number of redistributions is also dictated by the need to process waste containing precious elements or impurities harmful to the environment [2]. Instead, due to the involvement of new physical methods, the process of creating new materials can be simplified and made cheaper [3]. One of the options for quite simple and economical production of powder materials is the process of plasma-arc spraying of moving anode wires [4]. At the same time, an important problem is the minimization of the oxidation of the powders formed during such spraying. Therefore, this work is devoted to the study of the danger of oxidation of materials with

increased affinity to oxygen when they are sprayed by the chosen method.

The purpose of the work is to determine the propensity to oxygen saturation of materials with increased affinity for oxygen during their plasma-arc spraying in the case of using the process of spraying moving anode wires.

The scheme of the process of plasma-arc spraying of moving wires-anodes is presented in Fig. 1. A direct current arc burns between a refractory water-cooled cathode and a current-carrying wire located behind the plasmatron nozzle section. The working (plasma-forming) gas entering through the nozzle is heated by an electric arc and flows out of the nozzle in the form of a plasma jet. The open area of the discharge is blown by a flow of shielding gas, which is generally supplied at an angle to the axis of the plasma jet, the pressure in the external environment is atmospheric.

Fig.1. Scheme of the process of plasma-arc spraying of moving current-conducting wires-anodes.

Experimental studies of heating, melting and sputtering of conductive wires were carried out for two types of materials containing a metal with increased affinity for oxygen: wires with a diameter of 1.8 mm from aluminum-magnesium alloy 5083 and copper Cu99. Taking into account the fact that the oxidation of such active elements as aluminum and copper in the melting process negatively affects the spraying process and the service properties of the applied coatings, the experiments were carried out with the help of the original equipment (plasma-forming gas - argon) [5]. In this case, along the periphery of the plasmatron, an accompanying air flow is supplied through the channels, which cools the nozzle and compresses the high-temperature jet, which leads to a more uniform distribution of temperature fields along the radius of the plasma torch. The direction of such a flow is coaxial with the plasma jet, as a result of which the cone-shaped shape of the plasma jet is transformed into a cylindrical one. It is this form that indicates the equalization of both

pressure flows in the zones. This technological technique eliminates the admixture of oxygen, nitrogen, and hydrogen into the plasma, to which the selected sputtering materials have a high affinity for oxygen.

The analysis of the appearance and granulometric composition of selected samples of sprayed particles of aluminum and copper allows us to conclude that the size of the particles is in a wide range from 1 to 250 μm .

As a result of the analysis of the microstructure and chemical composition of the end of the wire-anode made of aluminum alloy 5083 after a sharp interruption of the arc, it was established that the molten zone (spectrum 1, fig. 2, table 1) is characterized by an increased oxygen content – 2.13 wt. %. In the direction from the melted end to the cold zone of the wire, there is a tendency to decrease the oxygen content. The transition zone (spectrum 2, Fig. 2, Table 1) is characterized by a lower percentage of oxidation (1.1 wt.% oxygen). The main metal of the wire, for which no thermal effect was detected, contains 0.37-0.90 wt. % oxygen (spectrum 4, Fig. 2, Table 1).

Fig. 2. The microstructure of the end of the anode wire made of aluminum alloy 5083 after a sharp interruption of the arc in the process of plasma-arc spraying.

Table 1.
Chemical composition of the local zones of the end of the wire-anode made of aluminum alloy 5083 after a sharp interruption of the arc in the process of plasma-arc spraying.

The numbers of the local zones of the regions shown in Fig. 2	Mass content of elements, %							
	O	Mg	Al	Si	Ar	Mn	Fe	Total
Spectrum 1	2,13	6,37	90,79	-	0,23	0,48	-	100
Spectrum 2	1,11	6,41	91,2	-	0,33	0,54	0,42	100
Spectrum 3	0,82	6,64	90,89	0,31	0,26	0,88	0,21	100
Spectrum 4	-	6,57	91,93	-	0,22	0,98	0,29	100
Spectrum 5	0,9	6,43	92,13	-	-	0,54	-	100
Spectrum 6	0,93	1,36	75,39	-	-	9,5	12,82	100
Spectrum 7	0,48	4,6	83,52	-	0,21	6,08	5,11	100
Spectrum 8	0,37	20,8	72,18	6,2	-	0,45	-	100

The electrode is an aluminum matrix with interspersed light phase. Microhardness in the melting zone is 1055 MPa. The base metal has a microhardness of 1062 MPa.

In the process of plasma-arc heating of the wire-anode from the studied aluminum alloy at its feed rate

of 0.2-0.4 m/min, the sputtering process is unstable, pulsations of the sputtered material flow are observed. The speed of particles reaches 95...110 m/s. Analysis of the granulometric composition of the particles that are sprayed shows that the largest number of them has a

size of 150...200 μm . The coefficient of material utilization is 0.60...0.63.

At an aluminum wire feed speed of 0.4-0.9 m/min, the molten material transfer process is stable. The size of most particles decreases and is 80...140 microns, and the material utilization factor reaches 0.65...0.70.

With an increase in the wire feed speed to 0.8-1.5 m/min, the values of the material utilization factor significantly decrease and amount to 0.5...0.6.

It is shown that when aluminum wire is sprayed at a feed speed of 0.2-0.4 m/min, the transfer mechanism is realized by large drops, and at a feed speed of 0.4-0.8 m/min, it is a jet mechanism. The nature of the dispersion affects the size and velocity of the particles of the atomized material. Thus, at a wire feed speed of 0.42 m/min, most of the particles have dimensions of 72...110 μm and their speed is 150-165 m/s.

In the event of a decrease in the air pressure, which cools the nozzle and compresses the high-temperature jet, the size of the sprayed aluminum and copper particles increases sharply. So, for example, at an aluminum wire feed speed of 0.4-0.9 m/min in the case of a decrease in air pressure from 7.0 to 4.5 MPa, the size of most particles is 150-200 μm , and the material utilization factor is about 0.6.

The conducted studies showed that sputtering of the electrode material from the selected aluminum alloy, in the process of plasma-arc heating, leads to an increase in the share of oxygen in the alloy by an average of 2.5 times (Fig. 3, Table 2).

A peculiarity of the structure of the end of the Cu99 copper wire anode after a sharp interruption of the arc in the process of plasma-arc spraying is the presence of eutectics in the form of dendrites (Fig. 4). As a result of micro-X-ray spectral chemical analysis (Table 3), it was established that the dendritic structure is formed due to the formation of copper oxides. The oxygen content in the zone of dendrite formation reaches 8-11 wt. %, while in the zone of minimal thermal influence of the copper wire-anode, the oxygen content is 1.2-1.3 wt. % (Fig. 4, Table 3).

It should be noted that in the case of a copper wire-electrode, in contrast to an electrode made of a selected aluminum alloy, it was established that the chemical composition of the material practically does not change in the process of plasma-arc spraying. The material obtained by plasma-arc spraying of Cu99 copper anode wire contains 1.1-1.2 wt. % of oxygen, which is almost the same value as for the zone of minimal thermal influence of the copper wire-anode (Fig. 5, Table 4).

Fig. 3. Microstructure of a layer of material obtained by plasma-arc spraying of anode wire from aluminum alloy 5083 with layer-by-layer chemical analysis.

Table 2.

Chemical composition of local zones of the material obtained by plasma-arc spraying of the anode wire from aluminum wire 5083.

The numbers of the local zones of the regions shown in Fig. 3	Mass content of elements, %								
	C	O	Mg	Al	Si	Ar	Mn	Fe	Total
Spectrum 2	5,12	5,6	5,24	81,63	0,96	0,22	0,68	0,56	100
Spectrum 3	5,91	3,44	5,18	83,58	0,61	0,17	0,66	0,43	100
Spectrum 4	5,9	4,4	5,03	82,7	0,57	0,27	0,66	0,48	100
Spectrum 5	3,05	-	-	-	-	-	0,81	96,14	100

Fig. 4. The microstructure of the end of a Cu99 copper anode wire after a sharp interruption of the arc in the process of plasma-arc spraying.

Table 3. Results of the chemical analysis of the end of the Cu99 copper anode wire after a sharp interruption of the arc in the process of plasma-arc spraying.

The numbers of the local zones of the regions shown in Fig. 4	Mass content of elements, %		
	O	Cu	Total
Spectrum 1	11,04	88,96	100
Spectrum 2	11,5	88,5	100
Spectrum 3	3,05	96,95	100
Spectrum 4	1,28	98,72	100
Spectrum 5	1,31	98,69	100
Spectrum 6	7,14	92,86	100
Spectrum 7	8,75	91,25	100

Fig. 5. Microstructure of the layer of material obtained by plasma-arc spraying of Cu99 copper anode wire.

Table 4. Results of chemical analysis of the layer of material obtained by plasma-arc spraying of Cu99 copper anode wire.

The numbers of the local zones of the regions shown in Fig. 5	Mass content of elements, %					
	C	O	Mn	Fe	Cu	Total
Spectrum 2	2,82	1,21	-	-	95,97	100
Spectrum 3	3,34	1,22	-	-	95,45	100
Spectrum 4	2,53	1,1	-	-	96,37	100
Spectrum 5	3,28	-	0,57	96,16	-	100

On the basis of the conducted research, it was established that the selected scheme of the plasmatron with an open self-spraying moving wire-anode and a flow of accompanying shielding gas (air) ensures reduced oxidation of the sprayed material of the electrode. To detect such an effect during plasma-arc spraying of electrode wires from materials containing elements with increased affinity for oxygen, the oxygen content in the sprayed coatings was investigated. At the same time, it was established that this oxygen content is: 1.1-1.2 wt. % – for Cu99 copper, 3.4-4.4 wt. % – for aluminum-magnesium alloy 5083.

References

1. Shanthar R., Chen K., Abeykoon C. Powder-Based Additive Manufacturing: A Critical Review of Materials, Methods, Opportunities, and Challenges // *Advanced Engineering Materials*, 2023, V. 25, 2300375. – 43 p. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1002/adem.202300375>
2. Wiśniewska P., Hejna A., Saeb M. R. Recycling and Processing of Waste Materials // *Materials*, 2023,

V. 16(2), 508. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma16020508>

3. Li N., Huang S., Zhang G., etc. Progress in additive manufacturing on new materials: A review // *Journal of Materials Science & Technology*, V. 35, Is. 2, 2019. – P. 242-269. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmst.2018.09.002>

4. Strogonov D.V., Korzhyk V.M., Jianglong Yi, Tunik A.Yu., Burlachenko O.M., Alyoshyn A.O. Influence of the parameters of the process of plasma-arc spheroidization of current-conducting wire from low-carbon steel on the granulometric composition of the produced powders // *The Paton Welding Journal*, #9, 2022. – P. 51-58. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37434/tpwj2022.09.09>

5. Korzhyk V.M., Khaskin V.Yu., Yuhui Yao et al. Influence of accompanying compressing air flow on the coating structure and properties in plasma-arc spraying by consumable current-conducting wire. *The Paton Welding Journal*, V. 2, 2022. – P. 3-10. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.37434/tpwj2022.02.01>